

RELATIVE FORAGE QUALITY OF *Cenchrus purpureus* AS INFLUENCED BY HARVEST AGE AND PLANT SPACING.

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ABSTRACT

Planting Napier grass with wider plant spacing could allow better forage productivity, and harvesting should be best carried out at an early stage of planting for better nutrient quality. A total land area of 1196m² was used for the experiment and was laid out in a 2 x 2 factorial, arranged in a split plot design consisting of the main plot (age at harvest) and the sub plot (plant spacing). The experiment involved 4 treatments (3week, 6week age at harvest and 1m x 1m, 1m x 0.5m plant spacing) and was replicated 5 times. The harvested samples at 3 weeks and 6 weeks were oven dried and milled. The results showed a significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in the crude fibre (CF), ash, dry matter intake (DMI), relative feed value (RFV) and decrease in the crude protein (CP), ether extract (EE), neutral detergent fibre (NDF), acid detergent lignin (ADL) and hemicellulose as age at harvest increased. The grass planted using 1m x 1m plant spacing had the highest CP (17.18%), ash (14.89%) and ADL (4.86%) content and the highest value of CF (18.37%) was recorded from the grass planted with 0.5m x 1m while other parameters were not significantly ($P > 0.05$) affected by plant spacing. Age at harvest and plant spacing had an effect on the nutrient composition of Napier grass. Grass spacing at 1m x 1m had the higher CP while the higher CF content was obtained at 1m x 0.5m. On the other hand, as the plant advanced in age, the quality of the grass decreased.

Keywords: Relative forage quality, *Cenchrus purpureus*, harvest age, nutritive value, plant spacing.

INTRODUCTION

Ruminants depend largely on crop residues during the long dry periods of the year for maintenance as well as production of meat, milk, skin and fibre. However, the main feed resources for ruminant animals are pastures, crop residues and other agro-industrial by-products. (Kibon and Ørskov, 1993). The feed shortage for ruminants can be alleviated by deliberately cultivating forages. Availability of high-quality sown forages is important such that their potential values lie in the provision of protein, vitamins and also the mineral elements that are lacking in natural pastures during the dry season (Bamikole *et al.*, 2004). In order to overcome these problems, intensive forage management systems exploiting land, labor and water resources coupled with utilization of suitable forage species need to be developed.

Napier grass is one of the important forage grasses for pastures in the tropics and is used as one of the major feeds for ruminants (Asmare 2016) with high production potential under a multi-cut harvesting regime. Animal performance mainly depends on the quantity and quality of forage available to livestock (Lazzarini *et al.*, 2009). It is important to determine the nutritional value of forage in livestock nutrition, because effective livestock production is related to the amount of nutrients in the forage (Schut *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, the aim of this study was to determine the effect of age at harvest and plant spacing on the proximate composition, fibre composition and relative forage quality of Napier grass.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental site

This experiment was carried out at the pasture unit of the Cattle Production Venture, Federal University of Agriculture, Abeokuta. Ogun State, and at the laboratories of the Department of Pasture and Range Management, (FUNAAB) and International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI), Ibadan.

Experimental procedure and design

The total land area of 1196m² (10m x5m per plot) was mapped out for the experiment. Two plant spacing and two harvest age were the factors in this experiment; 0.5m x 1m and 1m x 1m spacing and 3 WAC and 6 WAC. Therefore, plant was harvest at 3week and 6week of age. This experiment was subjected to 2 × 2 factorial experiment carried out in a split-plot design. The main plot is the two-harvest age (3 and 6weeks) while the sub plot is the two-plant spacing (1m x 1m, 0.5m x 1m). Therefore, it consists of 4 treatments and was replicated 5 times

Proximate and Fiber composition: The proximate composition (dry matter, crude protein, ether extract and ash) and fiber content (NDF, ADF, ADL, Cellulose and Hemicellulose) of the milled samples were determined using the Near Infrared Spectroscopy (NIRS) machine at the international livestock research institute (ILRI), Ibadan.

Relative forage quality

The relative forage quality which entails the Digestible dry matter (DDM), Dry matter intake (DMI) and Relative feed value (RFV) was determined by calculations after getting the result of the NDF and ADF.

DDM= 88.9- (0.779 x %ADF), DMI=120/ %NDF, RFV= (DDM x DMI) x1.29

Statistical analysis

Data collected was subjected to analysis of variance using SAS package and significant means was separated using Tukey's HSD (SAS 1999) at 5% level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The proximate parameters were significantly ($p<0.05$) affected by plant spacing except for dry matter content (DMC) and ether extract (EE). The CP and the EE content of the grass at 3WAC was higher ($p<0.05$) than that harvest at 6WAC (15.71%). The CF and ash content of the grass at 6WAC was significantly ($p<0.05$) higher than that harvested at 3WAC. The crude protein (CP) and ash content of the grass as affected by plant spacing was significantly higher for grass planted at 1m x 1m spacing than at 0.5m x 1m spacing. The crude fibre (CF) of the grass was affected by plant spacing significantly ($p<0.05$) with the grass planted at 0.5m x 1m having a higher content.

The fibre fractions were not significantly ($p>0.05$) affected by plant spacing except for ADL which was higher for the grass spaced at 1m x 1m. The NDF, ADL and hemicellulose content of the grass harvested at 3 WAC was significantly ($p<0.05$) higher at 3WAC.

The relative forage quality parameters as affected by plant spacing were not all significant. The effect of age at harvest on the DMI and RFV content of the grass was significantly ($p<0.05$) evident and higher at 6 WAC than that harvested at 3 WAC.

Table 1: Effect of harvest age and plant spacing on the proximate composition (%) of *Cenchrus purpureus*

Factors		DM	CP	CF	EE	Ash
Harvest age (WAC)	Plant spacing					
3		95.07	16.36 ^a	14.71 ^b	4.26 ^a	13.59 ^b
6		93.96	15.71 ^b	18.06 ^a	3.43 ^b	15.52 ^a
SEM		0.10	0.08	0.14	0.01	0.03
	1m x 1m	94.68	17.18 ^a	14.40 ^b	3.80	14.89 ^a
	0.5m x 1m	94.36	14.89 ^b	18.37 ^a	3.89	14.22 ^b
	SEM	0.12	0.04	0.13	0.03	0.07

^{a, b, c}: Means in same column with different superscript are significantly ($p<0.05$) different

DM = Dry matter, CP= Crude proteins, CF = Crude fibre, EE = Ether extract, WAC =Weeks After Cut-back, SEM = Standard Error of Mean

Table 2: Effect of harvest age and plant spacing on the fibre composition (%) of *Cenchrus purpureus*

Factors		NDF	ADF	ADL	Hemicellulose	Cellulose
Harvest age (WAC)	Plant spacing					
3		70.18 ^a	43.01	5.07 ^a	27.16 ^a	37.95
6		67.16 ^b	42.09	3.18 ^b	25.07 ^b	38.51
SEM		0.15	0.09	0.05	0.11	0.07
	1m x 1m	69.11	43.21	4.86 ^a	25.89	38.35
	0.5m x 1m	68.24	41.89	3.39 ^b	26.34	38.51
	SEM	0.19	0.10	0.06	0.13	0.08

^{a, b, c}: Means in same column with different superscript are significantly (p<0.05) different, NDF = Neutral detergent fibre, ADF = Acid detergent fibre, ADL = Acid detergent lignin, SEM = Standard Error of Mean, WAC = Weeks after cut-back

Table 3: Effects of plant spacing and age at harvest on the relative feed quality (%) of *Cenchrus purpureus*

Factors		DDM	DMI	RFV
Harvest age	Plant spacing			
3		55.39	1.71 ^b	122.58 ^b
6		56.11	1.79 ^a	129.37 ^a
SEM		0.07	0.004	0.39
	1m x 1m	55.24	1.74	124.13
	0.5m x 1m	56.26	1.76	127.82
	SEM	0.07	0.005	0.48

^{a, b, c}: Means in same column with different superscript are significantly (p<0.05) different, DDM = Digestible dry matter, DMI = Dry matter intake, RFV = Relative feed value, SEM = Standard Error of Mean, WAC = Weeks after cut-back

Discussion

The decrease in CP content in this study with advancement in age is in line with the findings of Dele (2012) and Tilahun et al. (2017) for *P. purpureum* and *P. pedicilatum*, respectively. Similarly, Bayble et al. (2007) and Ansah et al. (2010) reported for Napier grass a decreasing trend in CP content with increased in harvesting age. The higher crude protein content for the grass spaced at 1m x 1m as recorded in this study is in line with the findings of Tilahun et al. (2017) who reported different spacing for which the most spacious having the highest crude protein content. This could be as a result of the plant population stand of the different spacing involved in this study. The CF increased as the harvest age increased which is in line with Lounglawan et al. (2014). This is as a result of decrease in leaf to stem ratio as the grass advanced in age. The difference in the CF value of the grass as affected by spacing obtained in this study is similar to the findings of Ishiaku et al. (2016) and Munza et al. (2018) for Sorghum where they reported the highest CF content for the closely spaced sorghum. This could be

attributed to competition of plant to effectively utilize sunlight energy for photosynthesis as well as soil nutrient. The content of ash in this study increased as the grass increase in age which is in contrast to the Lounglawan *et al.* (2014) who reported the decrease in ash as the age increases. This could be due to excess nutrient in the soil. The ash content increased as the spacing increased which is in support of Tilahun *et al.* (2017) who reported the progressive increase of ash content is affected as spacing increase. This could be related to competition in the uptake of nutrient. The NDF in this study is in contrast to the submission of Tilahun *et al.* (2017) which stated that with advancement in plant age the concentration of NDF increases. This could be as a result of error in sampling techniques.

CONCLUSION

This study clearly shows that spacing and harvest age had a marked effect on the nutrient composition of *Cenchrus purpureus*. Plant spacing at 1m x 1m had the highest CP and the CF content was obtained at 1m x 0.5m. On the other hand, as the plant advance in age the quality of the grass decreases.

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